

INTERLAMINAR REINFORCEMENT OF CFRP LAMINATES USING ZANCHOR PROCESS

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ABSTRACT

The mode I fracture toughness, G_{IC} and G_{IR} , increased with the increase in the Zanchor density, Z . In addition, the rate of the mode I fracture toughness increase, G_{Z2} / G_{Z0} , was almost independent of the difference of matrix resin, whereas the amount of the mode I fracture toughness increase, $G_{Z2} - G_{Z0}$, was higher with the tough resin than that with the brittle resin. In terms of the stacking sequence, the Zanchor process was more effective for quasi isotropic (QI) specimens compared to cross ply (CP) specimens of the same Zanchor density. Moreover, the Zanchor process was effective to generate the fiber bridgings, resulting in the increase of the fracture toughness due to the “bridging effect”, during the mode I crack propagation process.

The mode II fracture toughness, G_{IIC} and G_{IIR} , increased with the increase in the Zanchor density, Z . In addition, the amount of the mode II fracture toughness increase, $G_{Z2} - G_{Z0}$, was almost independent of the difference of matrix resin, whereas the rate of the mode II fracture toughness increase, G_{Z2} / G_{Z0} , was lower with the tough resin than that with the brittle resin. In terms of the stacking sequence, there was no significant difference in the fracture toughness between the QI and CP specimens of the same Zanchor density. Moreover, the Zanchor process was effective to generate the entangled fiber bundles (EFB), resulting in the increase of the fracture toughness due to the “wedge effect”, during the mode II crack propagation process.

1 INTRODUCTION

In recent years, CFRP (Carbon Fiber Reinforced Plastics) has been widely used in various fields including the aerospace industry because of their superior properties such as high stiffness, high strength, low weight, and good chemical resistance. However, one of the most significant problems observed in a CFRP used in aerospace structures is delamination. Hence, various techniques have been developed to improve the interlaminar fracture toughness. The interlaminar reinforcement techniques used for the CFRP laminates are classified broadly into two types. First, applications of interlayer toughened

Figure 1: Schematic of Zanchor process.

Table 1: Fabricated materials.

Fiber/Resin	Stacking sequence	Zanchor density
STS-24K/RTM6	Cross ply (CP) [(0/90) ₄ /(90/0) ₄] _s	CP-Z0
		CP-Z1
		CP-Z2
	Quasi isotropic (QI) [(0/45/90/-45) ₂ /(-45/90/45/0) ₂] _s	QI-Z1

composites, such as T800S/3900-2B, applied to the primary structures of Boeing 787 have been examined and used in practice. Second, applications of through-the-thickness reinforcement method, such as stitching, Z-pinning, and three dimensional fabrics, have been actively studied in recent years [1-5].

The Zanchor technique, which is a through-the-thickness reinforcement methods, developed by Shikibo and Mitsubishi Heavy Industries, can effectively and inexpensively improve the interlaminar strength of composite laminates [6]. In the Zanchor process, in-plate yarns are entangled with each other by sticking them with special needles, as shown in Figure 1, where entangled fiber bundles (EFB) are generated. Previous studies investigated the fundamental mechanism of the Zanchor process [7,8]. However, the resin, which was used as the matrix in the CFRP laminates, was relatively brittle. Hence, it is necessary to clarify the effectiveness of the Zanchor process with different types of materials, such as fibers, resins, and stacking sequences, for applications to aerospace structures. In addition, the interlaminar fracture behavior of the Zanchor-reinforced composites should be studied in terms of the reliability and efficiency.

In this study, the effects of the material properties of a CFRP laminate on the modes I and II interlaminar fracture mechanism with the Zanchor process were investigated. In particular, the effects of the resin properties and stacking sequence were studied.

2 MATERIALS

CF/epoxy composite panels (STS-24K/RTM6, Toho Tenax/Hexcel) of cross ply (CP, [(0/90)₄/(90/0)₄]_s) and quasi isotropic (QI, [(0/45/90/-45)₂/(-45/90/45/0)₂]_s) were fabricated in a stacking sequence with a high-strength intermediate-modulus CF dry fabric and a high-toughness epoxy resin using a RTM (Resin Transfer Molding) process. The nominal thickness of the panels was in the range of 7.5-7.8 mm.

The two types of composite panels with different Zanchor densities Z1 and Z2 were fabricated to study the effect of the Zanchor density. The Zanchor density, Z, was defined as a non-dimensional parameter proportional to the amount of Zanchor process per unit area. The Zanchor density of Z2 was twice as much as that of Z1. A composite panel without the Zanchor process Z0 was also fabricated using the same materials for comparison. Table 1 lists the specifications of the fabricated materials investigated in the present study.

3 MODE I INTERLAMINAR FRACTURE TOUGHNESS TESTS

3.1 Experimental procedures

The tests on mode I fracture toughness were conducted using DCB (Double Cantilever Beam) specimens [9] as shown in Figure 2. The width, b , and initial crack length, a_0 , of the specimen were 10 mm and 55 mm, respectively. Aluminum blocks with a sectional area of 10 × 10 mm were bonded to the specimen to apply the mode I loading. The sides of the DCB specimens were painted in white to observe the crack growth behavior. Some specimens were alternately loaded and unloaded several times while measuring the crack extension; the other specimens were loaded monotonously until the crack extended to a prescribed length. The DCB tests were conducted on a screw-driven testing machine at a displacement

Figure 2: Schematic of DCB specimen.

rate of $d\delta / dt = 1 \text{ mm/min}$ under a displacement controlled condition. The specimens were not precracked.

The mode I fracture toughness of the Zanchor-reinforced composites can be calculated as the critical value of the energy release rate, G_I , given by the following equation [9].

$$G_{IC} = \frac{3}{2(2h)} \left(\frac{P}{b}\right)^2 \frac{\sqrt[3]{(bC)^2}}{\alpha_1} \quad (1)$$

where b , $2h$, and $C (= \delta/P)$ are the width, thickness, and compliance of the specimen, respectively. P is the load applied to the specimen. δ is the displacement of the loading point. α_1 and β_1 , which depend on the material properties, are the coefficients given by the C - a relations, which are determined experimentally using the following equation.

$$\frac{a}{2h} = \alpha_1 \sqrt[3]{bC} + \beta_1 \quad (2)$$

3.2 Experimental results

Figure 3 shows the crack resistance curves (R-curves) obtained from the DCB tests. Figures 3 (a), (b), and (c) show the results of the cross ply materials CP-Z0, CP-Z1, and CP-Z2, respectively. Figure 3 (d) shows the result of the quasi isotropic materials QI-Z1. The abscissa represents the crack extension, Δa , calculated using Eq. (2). The ordinate represents the mode I fracture toughness, G_{IC} and G_{IR} , calculated using Eq. (1). The black plots represent the experimental results obtained from the five trials. The red plots represent the average of the experimental results obtained from the five trials. As shown in Figure 3, the fracture toughness, G_{IC} and G_{IR} , of the Zanchor composites CP-Z1 and CP-Z2, respectively was considerably higher than that of the base composite CP-Z0; the fracture toughness, G_{IC} and G_{IR} , increased with the increase in the Zanchor density, Z . For all the Zanchor composites, shown in Figures 3 (b), (c), and (d), the fracture toughness, G_{IC} and G_{IR} , gradually increased with the increase in the crack extension. This tendency was similar to that observed in the composite with the brittle resin [7]. In terms of the stacking sequence, the Zanchor process was more effective for QI specimens compared to CP specimens of the same Zanchor density Z1.

Figure 4 shows the comparison of the mode I fracture toughness between the tough matrix and brittle matrix specimens [7]. The abscissa represents the Zanchor density, Z . The ordinate represents the mode I fracture toughness, G_{IR} , represented by the average value $\Delta a = 40 \text{ mm}$. The red and blue plots represent the tough and brittle matrices, respectively. G_{Z2} represents the mode I fracture toughness, G_{IR} , in CP-Z2. G_{Z0} represents the mode I fracture toughness, G_{IR} , in CP-Z0. The amount of the mode I fracture toughness increase in the case of the tough matrix was estimated using the following equation.

$$G_{Z2} - G_{Z0} = 1.8 \text{ kJ/m}^2 \quad (3)$$

The rate of the mode I fracture toughness increase in the case of the tough matrix was estimated using the following equation.

$$G_{Z2} / G_{Z0} = 3.1 \quad (4)$$

Figure 3: R-curves of DCB test.

Figure 4: Comparison of the mode I fracture toughness (CP).

The amount of the mode I fracture toughness increase in the case of the brittle matrix was estimated using the following equation.

$$G_{Z2} - G_{Z0} = 1.2 \text{ kJ/m}^2 \quad (5)$$

The rate of the mode I fracture toughness increase in the case of the brittle matrix was estimated using the following equation.

$$G_{Z2} / G_{Z0} = 3.3 \quad (6)$$

The amount of the mode I fracture toughness increase, $G_{Z2} - G_{Z0}$, was higher with the tough resin as the matrix, Eq. (3), compared to that with the brittle resin, Eq. (5). The rate of the mode I fracture toughness increase, G_{Z2} / G_{Z0} , with the tough resin, Eq. (4) was almost the same as that with the brittle resin, Eq. (6), though the base composite was different. In terms of the rate of the mode I fracture toughness increase, the Zanchor process was more effective when the tough resin was used as the matrix compared to the brittle resin.

The above results suggested that the mode I fracture toughness, G_{IC} and G_{IR} , increased with the increase in the Zanchor density, Z . This tendency was similar to that observed in the composite with the brittle resin [7], where the mode I fracture toughness, G_{IC} and G_{IR} , increased linearly with the increase in the Zanchor density, Z . In addition, the rate of G_{Z2} / G_{Z0} was almost independent of the difference of matrix resin, whereas the increase of $G_{Z2} - G_{Z0}$ was higher with the tough resin than that with the brittle resin. Moreover, the Zanchor process was more effective for QI specimens compared to CP specimens of the same Zanchor density.

3.3 Mode I fracture morphology

Figure 5 shows the side views of a DCB specimen. Figures 5 (a) and (b) show the fracture morphologies of CP-Z0, which is the base composite, and CP-Z2, which is the Zanchor composite, respectively. As shown in the figure, a large amount of fiber bridgings were observed in CP-Z2; the amount of fiber bridgings increased with the increase in the Zanchor density, Z . This tendency was similar to that observed in the Zanchor composite with the brittle resin [7], where the energy absorption caused by the debonding of bridged fibers was the dominant reinforcement mechanism under mode I loading (bridging effect). In other words, the increase of $G_{Z2} - G_{Z0}$ would be affected by the mechanical properties of the matrix resin. This presumption was consistent with the results discussed in the previous section.

The above results suggested that the Zanchor process was effective to generate the fiber bridgings, resulting in the increase of the fracture toughness due to the “bridging effect”, during the mode I crack propagation process.

(a) CP-Z0

(b) CP-Z2

Figure 5: Side views of a DCB specimen (crack growth direction: \Rightarrow).

4 MODE II INTERLAMINAR FRACTURE TOUGHNESS TESTS

4.1 Experimental procedures

Tests on the mode II fracture toughness were conducted using 4ENF (Four-point End Notched Flexure) specimens [10] as shown in Figure 6. The bending span, $2L$, width, b , and initial crack length, a_0 , of the specimen were 80 mm, 10 mm, and 30 mm, respectively. The sides of the 4ENF specimens were painted in white to observe the crack growth behavior. The specimens were alternately loaded and unloaded several times by moving the loading and supporting points; the initial crack length, a_0 , was set as 30 mm at the start of each loading process to evaluate the fracture toughness. A steel plate with a thickness of 0.1 mm was placed on the crack surface at the supporting point to reduce the friction. The 4ENF tests were conducted on a screw-driven testing machine at a displacement rate of $d\delta / dt = 1$ mm/min under a displacement controlled condition. The specimens were not precracked.

The mode II fracture toughness of the Zanchor-reinforced composites can be calculated as the critical value of the energy release rate, G_{II} , given by the following equation.

$$G_{IIC} = \frac{P^2 d^2}{2b^2(2h)^2\alpha_{II}} \quad (7)$$

where b and $2h$ are the width and thickness, respectively. $C (= \delta/P)$ is the compliance of the specimen. P is the load applied to the specimen. δ is the displacement of the loading point. d is the distance between the loading and supporting points. α_{II} and β_{II} , which depend on the material properties, are the coefficients given by the C - a relations. They are determined experimentally using the following equation [10].

$$\frac{ad^2}{(2h)^3} = \alpha_{II}(bC) + \frac{\beta_{II}}{(2h)^3} \quad (8)$$

4.2 Experimental results

Figure 7 shows the crack resistance curves (R-curves) obtained from the 4ENF tests. Figures 7 (a), (b), and (c) show the results of the cross ply materials CP-Z0, CP-Z1, and CP-Z2, respectively. Figure 7 (d) shows the result of the quasi isotropic material QI-Z1. The abscissa represents the crack extension, Δa , calculated using Eq. (8). The ordinate represents the mode II fracture toughness, G_{IIC} and G_{IIR} , calculated using Eq. (7). The black plots represent the experimental results obtained from the five trials. The red plots represent the average of the experimental results obtained from the five trials. As shown in Figure 7, the fracture toughness, G_{IIC} and G_{IIR} of the Zanchor composites, CP-Z1 and CP-Z2, respectively, was much higher than that of the base composite CP-Z0; the fracture toughness, G_{IIC} and G_{IIR} , increased with the increase in the Zanchor density, Z . This tendency was similar to that observed in the composite with the brittle resin [8]. However, in terms of the stacking sequence, there was no significant difference in the fracture toughness between the QI and CP specimens of the same Zanchor

Figure 6: Schematic of 4ENF specimen.

Figure 7: R-curves of 4ENF test.

Figure 8: Comparison of the mode II fracture toughness (CP).

density Z1.

Figure 8 shows the comparison of the mode II fracture toughness between the tough and brittle matrix specimens [8]. The abscissa represents the Zanchor density, Z . The ordinate represents the mode II fracture toughness, G_{IIR} , represented by the average value $\Delta a = 20$ mm. The red and blue plots represent the tough and brittle matrices, respectively. G_{Z2} represents the mode II fracture toughness, G_{IIR} , in CP-Z2. G_{Z0} represents the mode II fracture toughness, G_{IIR} , in CP-Z0. The amount of the mode II fracture toughness increase in the case of the tough matrix was estimated using the following equation.

$$G_{Z2} - G_{Z0} = 1.1 \text{ kJ/m}^2 \quad (9)$$

The rate of the mode II fracture toughness increase in the case of the tough matrix was estimated using the following equation.

$$G_{Z2} / G_{Z0} = 1.6 \quad (10)$$

The amount of the mode II fracture toughness increase in the case of the brittle matrix was estimated using the following equation.

$$G_{Z2} - G_{Z0} = 0.9 \text{ kJ/m}^2 \quad (11)$$

The rate of the mode II fracture toughness increase in the case of the brittle matrix was estimated using the following equation.

$$G_{Z2} / G_{Z0} = 2.5 \quad (12)$$

The amount of the mode II fracture toughness increase, $G_{Z2} - G_{Z0}$, with the tough resin, Eq. (9) was almost the same as that with the brittle resin, Eq. (11). The rate of the mode I fracture toughness increase, G_{Z2} / G_{Z0} , was lower with the tough resin as the matrix, Eq. (10), compared to that with the brittle resin, Eq. (12). In terms of the amount of the mode II fracture toughness increase, the effect of the Zanchor process was almost the same regardless of the type of resin used as the matrix.

The above results suggested that the mode II fracture toughness, G_{IIC} and G_{IIR} , increased with the increase in the Zanchor density, Z . This tendency was similar to that observed in the composite with the brittle resin [8], where the mode II fracture toughness, G_{IIC} and G_{IIR} , increased linearly with the increase in the Zanchor density, Z . In addition, the increase of $G_{Z2} - G_{Z0}$ was almost independent of the difference of matrix resin, whereas the rate of G_{Z2} / G_{Z0} was lower with the tough resin than that with the brittle resin. Moreover, there was no significant difference in the fracture toughness between the QI and CP specimens of the same Zanchor density.

4.3 Mode II fracture morphology

Figure 9 shows the fracture surface of a 4ENF specimen. Figures 9 (a) and (b) show the fracture morphologies of CP-Z0, which is the base composite, and CP-Z2, which is the Zanchor composite, respectively. As shown in Figure 9 (a), the fracture surface was relatively flat and smooth for the base composite CP-Z0. However, as shown in Figure 9 (b), the fracture surface was rough for the Zanchor composite CP-Z2. The roughness of the fracture surface clearly increased with the increase in the Zanchor density, Z ; the fracture surface was formed because of the effect of the entangled fiber bundles (EFB). In addition, although a significant amount of fiber bridgings were observed in the mode I fracture surface, no fiber bridgings were observed in the mode II fracture surface, regardless of the Zanchor density. This tendency was similar to that observed in the Zanchor composite with the brittle resin [8], where the energy absorption caused by the breakage of EFB was the dominant reinforcement mechanism under mode II loading (wedge effect). In other words, the increase of $G_{Z2} - G_{Z0}$ would not be affected by the mechanical properties of the matrix resin. This presumption was consistent with the results discussed in the previous section.

The above results suggested that the Zanchor process was effective to generate the EFB, resulting in the increase of the fracture toughness due to the ‘‘wedge effect’’, during the mode II crack propagation process.

Figure 9: Fracture surface of a 4ENF specimen (crack growth direction: \Rightarrow).

5 CONCLUSIONS

The mode I interlaminar fracture behavior and the effectiveness of the Zanchor-reinforced composite laminates were investigated using DCB specimens. The results are summarized as follows:

- The mode I fracture toughness, G_{IC} and G_{IR} , increased with the increase in the Zanchor density, Z .
- The rate of G_{Z2} / G_{Z0} was almost independent of the difference of matrix resin, whereas the increase of $G_{Z2} - G_{Z0}$ was higher with the tough resin than that with the brittle resin.
- The Zanchor process was more effective for QI specimens compared to CP specimens of the same Zanchor density.
- The Zanchor process was effective to generate the fiber bridgings, resulting in the increase of the fracture toughness due to the “bridging effect”, during the mode I crack propagation process.

The mode II interlaminar fracture behavior and the effectiveness of the Zanchor-reinforced composite laminates were investigated using the 4ENF specimens. The results are summarized as follows:

- The mode II fracture toughness, G_{IIC} and G_{IIR} , increased with the increase in the Zanchor density, Z .
- The increase of $G_{Z2} - G_{Z0}$ was almost independent of the difference of matrix resin, whereas the rate of G_{Z2} / G_{Z0} was lower with the tough resin than that with the brittle resin.
- There was no significant difference in the fracture toughness between the QI and CP specimens of the same Zanchor density.
- The Zanchor process was effective to generate the EFB, resulting in the increase of the fracture toughness due to the “wedge effect”, during the mode II crack propagation process.

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